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Review Article

Systemic Review: Novel Approach for Solid Lipid Nanoparticles to Treat Pityriasis Versicolor

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ABSTRACT

Solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) are a novel drug delivery system for the treatment of pityriasis versicolor, a skin infection of fungal origin from Malassezia species. SLNs encapsulate the antifungal agents therefore it increasing bioavailability, stability and reducing systemic side effects. Targeted drug delivery through the nanoscale carriers results in enhanced treatment efficacy and recurrence reduction. Antifungal agent-controlled and sustained release results in the increased clearance of the lesions and cure rates. SLNs provide deeper penetration into skin, circumventing the constraint of traditional topical preparations. Patient compliance is enhanced by reduced frequency of applications necessary for traditional treatments. SLNs can be customised with a range of antifungal compounds, making them an effective and versatile drug delivery system. Yet, stability concerns, drug expulsion, and regulatory approval must be overcome for clinical acceptance. Complex formulation approaches like polymer coating and surfactant optimisation can help improve SLN performance. Further studies should optimise nanoparticle size, drug loading efficiency, and long-term stability. Clinical trials are necessary to confirm the safety, efficacy, and commercial viability of SLN-based antifungal therapies. This review highlights the promise of SLNs in transforming dermatological treatments for fungal infections.

INTRODUCTION

Solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs), is also called lipospheres, are the pharmaceutical nanocarriers intended for controlled drug delivery^[1,2]. Solid lipid nanoparticle is formulated with biodegradable and also with

safe lipidic constituents. The SLNs can be delivered to various therapeutics including small drug molecules, large drug molecules, genetic material and vaccine antigens. Among the small drug molecules are loaded in both hydrophilic and lipophilic drugs^[3,4]. The internal core structure of solid lipid nanoparticles provides space to

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accumulate lipophilic molecules. Being very tiny particles of nanosize ranges, the presented advantages related to biopharmaceutical aspects of nanoparticle following their in- vivo

administration and controlled release of loaded componets at desired site of action for better therapeutic action^[5].

Figure No. 1 Solid Lipid Nanoparticle

Advantages Of Solid Lipid Nanoparticles For Topical Application ^[6,7]

- Solid lipid nanoparticles well penetrate the skin at outermost layer that allow deep delivery and target to site of action.
- Solid lipid nanoparticles help to improve the bioavailability drugs which are of poorly soluble and the drugs are encapsulated within lipid matrices.
- Solid lipid nanoparticles improves stability
- Solid lipid nanoparticles also improve the shelf life.
- Solid lipid nanoparticles help to improve therapeutic effect at site of action.
- Solid lipid nanoparticles are used because they reduce the irritation compared to other delivery system.
- The solid lipid nanoparticles carrier they help to reduce biotoxicity.

Disadvantage ^[8,9]

- Solid lipid nanoparticles have the crystalline structure which limits the available for encapsulating drugs.

- In solid lipid nanoparticles Physical stability became an issue because of aggregation and also for changes in particle size during storage condition.
- Sometimes unexpected dynamic changes in polymeric transitions.
- Sometimes degradation occurs in products of lipid and also present a safety risk based on formulation.

Types For Solid Lipid Nanoparticles

• Type I Homogeneous Matrix Model

SLN type 1 be identified as one of the models for solid solutions because the active ingredient is molecularly dispersed in the lipid core or it may exist as amorphous clusters. It thus is a model of homogeneous matrix, and it is derived based on HPH or cold homogenization procedures performed at temperatures above the melting point of lipids^[10]. This pharmaceutical agent is cold homogenized without the incorporation of surfactants or solubility-enhancing agents so that it may be dispersed at a molecular level. The pharmaceutical compound interacts extensively with the lipid component ^[11,15].

• **Type II Drug Enriched Shell Model**

SLN type 2 is prepared via a homogenization process initiated by heat induction. This theory suggests that at the recrystallization temperature of the lipid, the solid lipid core is formed. When the temperature of the dispersion is lowered, the o/w nanoemulsion undergoes lipid precipitation, which elevates the drug concentration in the liquid lipid phase. The drug tends to concentrate in the outer shell of the solid lipid nanoparticles, which remains in a liquid state. drug concentration locally and enhances antifungal activity, thus managing the infection effectively and reducing the chance of recurrence. Therefore, solidification of the outer shell encapsulates a large portion of the drug within it. Earlier formulations generally caused a burst drug release and led to dose dumping. Such earlier developments were usually achieved under low lipid concentrations in the liquid phase, and thus, were insufficient for sustained drug release [10,11].

• **SLNs Type III Drug Enriched Core Model**

SLN type 3 is drug precipitation proceeds re-solidification. This happens after the drug concentration in the lipid has reached or exceeded the limit of solubility saturation as a result of high drug loading into the matrix of the lipids [12,15]. Thus, on cooling, the supersaturation levels of the nanoemulsion reaches with respect to the drug remain high, followed by lipid resolidification following drug precipitation. The core, enriched with drug molecules, assumes a membrane-like structure and, as the temperature continues to decrease, the lipid recrystallizes around it. Such a model is generally suitable for drugs requiring an extended-release profile within a certain time frame [13,14].

Figure no. 2 Models of incorporation of active compounds into SLNs [15,73]

Role of Solid lipid nanoparticles to treat PV
[16,17,18]

- SLNs encapsulate the drug and enhance the bioavailability of antifungal agents.
- The better penetration of SLNs into the skin layers, thus ensuring better targeting to areas where Malassezia species reside.
- SLNs provide controlled and sustained release of the drug, which results in reduced

application frequency and, hence, higher compliance among patients.

- Biocompatibility of the lipids used in SLNs reduces irritation and improves tolerability; hence, it can be used for sensitive or compromised skin.
- They can be formulated into creams, gels, or even sprays to conveniently enhance their adaptability to suit every patient's needs.
- It can include stimuli-responsive systems that are sensitive to pH and temperature as a means for controlled drug release suited to the specific condition of the skin.
- SLNs can be used to deliver both lipophilic and hydrophilic antifungal agents that ensure versatility in their use to treat different cases.

Effective treatment of SLN ^[71,72]

1. Superior Skin Penetration:

SLNs have shown enhanced penetration of drugs into the stratum corneum and deeper skin layers compared to conventional creams or lotions. The nanoscale size of SLNs improves their ability to cross the lipid barriers of the skin, thus delivering antifungal agents such as ketoconazole, fluconazole, itraconazole or terbinafine directly to the site of infection^[19]. This targeted delivery mechanism enhances the therapeutic outcome while minimizing drug wastage and systemic exposure^[20].

2. Faster Lesion Clearance:

Clinical studies have indicated that SLN-based formulations show a faster clearance of fungal lesions and a significant reduction in the fungal load as compared with conventional antifungal preparations. The sustained release properties of drugs from SLNs result in extended antifungal activity and reduced cumulative fungal burden efficiently over time ^[19,20,21].

3. Higher rates of clinical and mycological cure:

Patients treated with SLN-based antifungal formulations have higher rates of both clinical cure (the visible resolution of symptoms) and mycological cure (eradication of the fungal organisms)^[20]. Such double effectiveness not only provides quicker relief from symptoms but also reduces the possibility of relapse.

4. Enhanced Stability and Bioavailability:

The lipid matrix of SLNs protects encapsulated antifungal agents from degradation due to environmental effects such as light, heat or oxidation. This enhances the shelf life and bioavailability of the active ingredient, ensuring constant therapeutic efficacy over the length of treatment ^[21,22].

5. Minimal side effects:

SLN-based formulations are capable of delivering drugs locally with minimum systemic absorption and, thus, associated adverse effects. Patients are also less prone to irritation, redness, or sensitivity than in the case of traditional topical antifungal treatments ^[19].

6. Reduced Recurrence Rates:

The deep penetration along with sustained action of SLNs prevents fungal infections from coming back again. This is very useful in the case of Pityriasis Versicolor as this condition often tends to recur ^[20,21].

7. Versatile Drug Delivery System:

SLNs can be used to encapsulate a wide range of hydrophilic and lipophilic antifungal drugs, making it a versatile and adaptable delivery system. They may also be used in combination

with other active ingredients, such as anti-inflammatory agents, to enhance therapeutic outcomes further [21,22].

Antifungal Agent

Antifungal agents are drugs or chemicals that inhibit the growth otherwise kill fungal pathogens they are used to treat mycoses in humans, animals and plants [23,24,25,26]. Fungal infections can be superficial and systemic meaning that life

threatening infections. Superficial fungal infection occurs in the outermost like skin, hair and mucous membrane and they can be caused by a variety of fungi like dermatophytes, yeast and molds. They may spread through contact or contaminated environmental source and their prevalence is on rise among both community and healthcare setting [75,76].

Table no. 1 Common uses for topical antifungal [23]

CONDITION	COMMONLY USED DRUGS
Athelet foot (Tinea pedis)	Terbinafine, clotrimazole, miconazole, tolnaftate
Pityriasis versicolor (Tinea versicolor)	Terbinafine, itraconazole fluconazole, miconazole
Jock itch (Tinea cruris)	Miconazole, naftifine, clotrimazole
Vaginal candidiasis	Miconazole, clotrimazole, nystatin
Oral thrush	Nystain, clotrimazole
Seborrheic dermatitis	Ketoconazole, ciclopirox
Fungal nail infection	Ciclopirox, efinaconazole, tavaborole

Pityriasis Versicolor

Pityriasis versicolor is also called as tinea versicolor is a superficial fungal infection result for the proliferation of malassezia species inside the stratum corneum on skin layer [27,24]. Malassezia species act pathogenic when it behave like the mycelial under the influence of trigger factor, including humidity, immunosuppression and hyperhidrosis [28]. For that PV is more occurred in humid tropical than in cold temperature. Therefore, the yeast most often becomes pathogenic in tropical temperature, affecting up to 50%-60% of the population in those condition. Cure percentage of PV is often difficult to achieve the goal because setback after treatment can occur in two year [29,30]. Topical antifungals are prolong effective in treatment of pityriasis versicolor fungal infections, but systemic antifungals are advised for severe or incorrigible cases. In some cases non-specific topical treatments are working in the management of PV. The

penetration of antifungal agents inside the dermis layer of the skin is desirable because fungal hyphae (mycelium) can be penetrated deeply through the epidermal layers. Due to the prolong penetration and retention in the skin by SLN based topical gel, whose formulation is lipid nano in nature topical treatment and symptomatic relief of fungal infection occur in promising way [31,24].

History of Pityriasis versicolor [32]

- The history of Pityriasis versicolor a superficial infection caused by fungi which causes discoloured spots on skin which has a history goes back more than 150 years. The disorder is primarily caused by yeasts of the genus Malassezia, but these exist and live saprophytically on healthy skin and they change to a pathogenic form under certain situations.
- An important in dermatological mycology was achieved in 1846 when Eichstedt identified these yeasts as pathogens for the first time. A large number of studies carried out over the

years have shown that both hereditary and environmental factors can be involved in the causation of the disease in tropical and humid areas where up to 40% of the population may be affected by the disease is more prevalent. The presence of Malassezia yeasts has been established by microscopic methods and clinical evaluation. Although common, pityriasis versicolor often goes unreported due to its asymptomatic nature.

Figure no. 3

Figure no. 4

Figure no. 3,4 images of Pityriasis versicolor on Skin

Table no. 2 Pathogenesis of pityriasis versicolor ^(32,70)

Topical Treatment for Pityriasis Versicolor

Effective topical treatments for Pityriasis Versicolor (PV) including creams, lotions, and shampoos, improve symptoms quickly but may face compliance issues due to frequent application or irritation^(33,34). Non-specific agents like selenium sulfide and zinc pyrithione remove infected tissue but do not target *Malassezia* species. Antifungals such as Fluconazole, Itraconazole, Clotrimazole, Miconazole are effective, with newer options like ciclopirox olamine showing higher efficacy. Well-studied, modern treatments like ketoconazole and terbinafine have their future focus on novel delivery systems such as solid lipid nanoparticles that are believed to provide increased efficacy and improve patient adherence^(34,35,36).

Mechanism of action of drugs used to treat pityriasis versicolor

Fluconazole

Fluconazole is loaded in solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) designed for topical therapy for Pityriasis versicolor by providing accurate and effective drug delivery. These nanoparticles would allow for greater stability of drugs, deep penetration inside the stratum corneum, and targeted accumulation in sebaceous-rich areas where *Malassezia* species reside. Fluconazole encapsulated in the lipid matrix, inhibit the fungal enzyme lanosterol 14 α demethylase, disrupting ergosterol synthesis and compromising fungal cell membrane integrity. The nanoparticle size and lipid nature of SLNs allow them to overcome skin barrier while providing controlled and sustained drug release, ensuring prolonged antifungal activity exposure, enhance therapeutic outcomes and aligns with patient friendly non invasive treatment paradigms making it a

promising advancement in managing pityriasis versicolor^(37,38).

Ketoconazole

Ketoconazole is loaded in solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) which is good at the present time for a modern approach to treating Pityriasis versicolor by combination with superior drug delivery with targeted antifungal activity. Ketoconazole in the form of a lipid matrix therefore it will enhance the desired stability penetration deep into skin and controlled release. These lipid based nanoparticles penetrate deep into stratum corneum and sebaceous glands and thus targeting to *Malassezia* species directly. Ketoconazole will inhibit the fungal cytochrome P450 enzymes such as lanosterol 14 α -demethylase hence it interrupting ergosterol synthesis and compromising the integrity of the fungal cell membrane. The controlled release mechanism of SLNs maintains constant drug levels at the site of infection thereby enhancing therapeutic effect while by reducing systemic exposure and side effects. This innovative method help to enhance effective and localized treatment by improved patient compliance and reducing irritation by representing a significant advantage in treating Pityriasis versicolor^(39,40,41).

Terbinafine

Terbinafine is loaded in solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) form an advanced way of treating Pityriasis versicolor because it enhance drug stability, penetration and controlled release. Terbinafine is fungicidal therefore it will inhibits the action of the fungal enzyme like squalene epoxidase which plays an important role in the biosynthesis of ergosterol in the fungal cell membrane. Such inhibition leads to the accumulation of toxic squalene, disrupting the integrity of cell membranes and hence causing

death to the fungal cells. SLNs are a new system for the encapsulation of terbinafine, improving its solubility and enabling better penetration of the skin into deeper areas, including stratum corneum and sebaceous glands where the *Malassezia* species resides. The sustained release of the lipid nanoparticles minimizes systemic absorption but prolongs the therapeutic action at the infection site. Terbinafine-loaded SLNs further enhance biocompatibility with the skin and thus reduce irritation to improve treatment efficacy. This novel delivery system holds a lot of promise as a future patient-friendly, effective solution for the topical management of Pityriasis versicolor^(42,43,44).

Griseofulvin

Griseofulvin loaded-solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) offer a futuristic solution for the topical treatment of Pityriasis versicolor by enhancing drug solubility, stability, and skin penetration. Griseofulvin disrupts fungal cell division by binding to fungal microtubules and inhibiting mitosis. It also accumulates in keratin-rich cells, creating an environment unfavorable for fungal growth and persistence. The encapsulation of griseofulvin in SLNs would ensure targeted delivery to the stratum corneum and sebaceous glands, where *Malassezia* species are found. The nanoparticles offer sustained drug release,

maintaining consistent therapeutic levels at the site of infection while reducing systemic absorption and possible side effects. The lipid matrix simulates skin lipids, ensuring compatibility and minimizing irritation. This new delivery system offers a promising advance for localized, effective, and patient-friendly management of Pityriasis versicolor^(45,46).

Itraconazole

Itraconazole loaded in solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) to treat topically Pityriasis versicolor which helps in enhancing drug delivery, stability and efficacy. Itraconazole is an antifungal drug by the inhibition of ergosterol synthesis. The important component of fungal cell membranes which act by inhibiting 14 α -demethylase. This inhibition disrupts the fungal membrane, which eventually causes cell death. Encapsulation of itraconazole in a lipid matrix in SLNs protects the drug and helps in sustained release and increased retention on the skin. The particle size of the SLNs being small, improves penetration into the stratum corneum, which further delivers itraconazole at the site of infection with reduced systemic exposure. Moreover, SLNs create an occlusive film on the skin surface, which prolongs the action^(47,48).

Table No. 3 Physicochemical Properties and Stability Parameters

compound	Particle size	Polydispersity Index (PDI)	Zeta potential	EE%	Product yield	P ^{ka}	Optimal P ^H stability	Ref. No.
Fluconazole	174.5-300nm	0.1-0.3M	-20 to -30mV	60% to 80%	70-90%	.8-9.3	5.0-7.5	37, 38
Ketoconazole	150– 500nm	0.2- 0.5M	-15 to -25mV	50% to 75%	60 -80%	2.9	≤ 4.0	39, 40
Terbinafine	200– 400nm	0.1 - 0.4M	-10 to -20mV	70% to 90%	75 – 95%	7.1	7.0-8.0	42, 43

Griseofulvin	200– 600nm	0.3 – 0.6M	-5 to -15mV	60% to 85%	65 – 85%	5.4	5.0-7.0	45, 46
Itraconazole	100-300nm	0.1-0.3M	-15 to -35mV	60% to 90%	75%- 92%	3.7	5.0-7.0	47, 48

Table no. 4 Method of Preparation for SLN (49,50,67)

Method of Preparation of Solid lipid nanoparticle

1. High Pressure Homogenization (HPH)

A) Hot Homogenization:

- **Process:** The lipid is melted above the melting point. The drug then gets incorporated into this molten lipid^(51,52,53). This drug-lipid mixture is now emulsified with an aqueous phase containing the emulsifier. The resultant pre-emulsion is then carried out under homogenization processes at high pressures (100-2000 bar). This narrows down to a gap through which the pre-emulsion is forced and

results in the size reduction of droplets of lipids. The high Shear forces and cavitation result in a reduction in particle size, usually resulting in nanoparticles within the submicron range^(51,52,54,55).

B) Cold Homogenization:

- **Process:** This process does not melt the lipid rather, the lipid and drug are mixed in their solid states, then submitted to high-pressure homogenization in an aqueous phase, just like in hot homogenization. This method is helpful for heat-sensitive drugs because it avoids thermal degradation^(49,56).

2. Ultrasonication

- **Process:** This method involves the use of ultrasonic waves that generate high shear forces responsible for breaking lipid particles apart^(57,58). It is possible to do this either with a probe sonicator or a bath sonicator. It produces smaller particle sizes however, it causes metal contamination and physical instability^(59,60).

3. Supercritical Fluid Method

- **Process:** This is a relatively new technique, in which supercritical carbon dioxide acts as a solvent. The lipid is dissolved in supercritical CO₂, and upon rapid expansion, it precipitates to form nanoparticles. This is a solvent free method that can give dry powders rather than suspensions^(61,62,63).

4. Microemulsion Based Method

- **Process:** The microemulsion is prepared by combining a low-melting fatty acid, emulsifiers, and water. This hot microemulsion is then diluted with cold water which leads to the creation of SLNs. Droplet structure in the microemulsion is pre-formed. No extra energy input is needed for size reduction^(49,56).

5. Precipitation Technique

- **Process:** An organic solvent, such as chloroform, dissolves the lipid, which then emulsifies into the aqueous phase. After the solvent has evaporated, particles of the lipid precipitate to make nanoparticles. This technique is simple but demands precise control of solvent removal⁽⁴⁹⁾.

6. Solvent Injection Technique

- **Process:** The lipid is dissolved in a water-miscible solvent, for example, ethanol, and then injected into a stirred aqueous phase. To stabilize the formed lipid droplets during injection, emulsifiers are used. This technique is speedy and not involved with high technology equipment⁽⁶⁴⁾.

Evaluation of SLNs

Physical evaluation

The SLN formulations were off-white with semi-solid texture. The pH was between 7.0 and 8.0, which is appropriate for dermal use. Rheological investigations indicated non-Newtonian flow behavior, which suggests shear-thinning characteristics conducive to topical use. The viscosity values decreased with spindle speed increase, which verifies their suitability for use in diverse formulations. These characteristics ensure stability and easy application of the formulation^(65,66).

Particle size and Zeta potential

Particle size analysis indicated that the optimized formulations possessed mean diameters in the favorable nanometer range (100–500 nm)⁽⁶⁵⁾. Zeta potential measurements yielded values of between -15.3 and -43.2 mV, demonstrating stable nanoparticles. Smaller particle sizes and greater stability are essential for successful drug delivery and enhanced skin penetration. These features validate the efficiency of the formulation^(67,64).

Drug content and In vitro release studies

Drug content analysis exhibited high homogeneity between the formulations, with values greater than 94%. In vitro release studies showed sustained drug release behavior over 24 hours, which is desirable for long-term therapeutic action⁽⁶⁹⁾. SLNs released the drug more slowly and in a

controlled manner compared to the commercial formulation, indicating their potential to improve patient compliance⁽⁶⁵⁾.

Differential Scanning Calorimetry(DSC) and Scanning Electron Microscopy(SEM)

DSC analysis indicated the lack of important interactions between excipients and the drug, ensuring the stability of the active ingredient. SEM studies showed that SLNs possessed smooth, spherical surfaces, which improved their stability and potential for application. The results are in line with the structural integrity and biocompatibility of the formulation with the skin^(66,68).

Stability Studies

Short-term stability tests at $40^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $75\% \pm 5\%$ RH for four weeks revealed no appreciable change in drug content, release pattern, or physical appearance. The findings verify the formulation's stability under accelerated conditions, which ensures the product's effectiveness over time^(66,67).

Characteristics of Solid lipid nanoparticles^(71,72)

- Solid lipid nanoparticles size ranges from 50-1000nm but some formulation aim for 200-500nm.
- Solid lipid nanoparticles can incorporated both hydrophilic and lipophilic drugs.
- Solid lipid nanoparticles can increase bioavailability to improve drug stability and permeability.
- Encapsulation efficiency have ranges between 50%-90% where it depends on drug solubility and formulation method.
- Reduce the drug leakage and degradation when compared with liquid lipid carriers
- Solid lipid nanoparticle have ability to penetrate deep into the skin and give therapeutic effect at site of action.

Application For Solid lipid nanoparticles to treat Pityriasis versicolor^(72,73,74)

- By using Solid lipid nanoparticles can improve the skin penetration and poor permeability through the stratum corneum.
- This formulation help to reduce the systemic adverse effect such as hepatotoxicity.
- Solid lipid nanoparticles improve the adherence by treating other chronic skin infection.
- They are approached for sever and cyclic fungal infection resistant as a standard treatment.
- Solid lipid nanoparticles provide a prolong release.
- Solid lipid nanoparticles provide controlled release by reducing the frequency of application and improving patient compliance.
- Solid lipid nanoparticles could be combined with genomics to create personalized topical formulations suited to patient specific condition.

Challenges occurs in Solid lipid nanoparticle

- Solid lipid nanoparticles will undergo in physical state which changes during storage and leading to drug expulsion and reduce the effect.
- There are lack of sufficient in-vivo studies are done to confirm Solid lipid nanoparticles safety and effectiveness in clinical application.
- When drug incorporated within the solid lipid nanoparticles it may be expelled overtime because of changes in environmental condition and formulation stability.
- The stability of Solid lipid nanoparticles formulation is critical because of change in the crystalline structure and may also change in drug release profiles and compromise long term stability.

- The novel nature of solid lipid nanoparticles with an additional safety and efficacy requirements compared with traditional formulation systems and limiting factor that hinders through regulatory approvals and widespread absorption.

Future direction

- The future research should be focus on optimizing lipid composition and surfactant then also enhance the drug loading capacity and stability.
- It reduces the drug expulsion late over.
- Solid lipid nanoparticles should also have surface modification such as ligand attachment for cancer therapy and infectious diseases.
- Solid lipid nanoparticles help to enhance the bioavailability of poorly soluble drugs for better absorption through lymphatic transport and enzymatic protection.
- Solid lipid nanoparticles help to minimize skin irritation and allergic reaction and help to treat long term topically.

DISCUSSION

The introduction of solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) is a revolutionary step in drug delivery, especially for topical dermatological treatment such as Pityriasis versicolor. The nanoscale dimensions, biocompatibility, and capability of encapsulating both hydrophilic and lipophilic drugs are highly efficient. One of the main strengths of SLNs is their improved penetration into the skin, enabling antifungal compounds to penetrate deep into the layers where *Malassezia* species reside, ensuring effective treatment with less systemic side effects. Their sustained and controlled drug release minimizes application frequency, enhancing patient compliance and therapeutic drug level sustainment for prolonged efficacy. This is especially useful for chronic and

recurrent infections, allowing for accelerated lesion clearance and minimized fungal load. Furthermore, SLNs also provide increased drug stability and bioavailability, avoiding premature degradation. Optimization of lipid composition, surfactant systems, and surface modifications can enhance drug loading and stability. Stimuli-responsive systems can further optimize SLNs to enable personalized therapeutic strategies. Overcoming these challenges can revolutionize antifungal therapy, and SLNs can become a safe and effective treatment for Pityriasis versicolor and other dermatological diseases.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) are an important breakthrough in the topical therapy of Pityriasis versicolour. With their capacity for increased skin penetration and delivery of antifungal drugs to the site of infection, coupled with controlled and prolonged drug release, they are an effective treatment method. SLNs not only increase overall bioavailability and stability of encapsulated drugs but also provide a more patient-friendly option by decreasing the application frequency and lowering systemic side effects. Beyond already present drawbacks in the form of formulation stability and additional clinical studies needed, future research focused on optimising SLN systems promises to address better outcomes for patients in treating Pityriasis versicolour and other dermatological diseases.

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